

UOTF in The Digital Age: Enhancing the Wellbeing of B40 Youth in Nigeria Through University International Community Engagement Activities and Digital Platform

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Abstract: For an economy to attain overall greatness and steady growth there has to be strategies planned and implemented. An achieving and stable economy should offer quality education, good health facilities and services, little or no poverty, job opportunities and fence gender inequality as these are the building blocks of humans and the society at large. This paper offers a conceptual business model for a Malaysian University-of-the-Future (UotF) with the value proposition of enhancing the societal wellbeing of B40 youth in Nigeria through digital platform and university international community engagement (UICE) activities with focus on balanced entrepreneurship education. Enhancing societal wellbeing include balanced education, reduced poverty, decent work and economic growth, good health and gender fairness. The conceptual business model is developed through understanding the needs of B40 youth in Nigeria by using business modeling tools i.e. Business Model Canvas (BMC) and Value Proposition Design Canvas (VPC). The approach involves carrying out a literature review and interviews to identify key issues of Customer Segments, formulating and devising an initial business model – in the form of BMC and VPC, and value proposition that helps to enhance the wellbeing of B40 youth in Nigeria. The contribution of this paper is a conceptual business model of the Malaysian UotF which includes a digital platform and university international community engagement (UICE) activities with focus on balanced entrepreneurship education. The UotF business model proposed in this paper will aid communities and the general society in Nigeria to acquire the relevant skills, knowledge, values, and platform needed to furnish the societal wellbeing.

Keywords: Societal well-being, B40 youth, University-of-the-Future, Digital Age, Nigeria, SDG, BMC, VPC, Balanced entrepreneurship education, International Community engagement.

1. INTRODUCTION

“Beyond the immediate educational goal is the question of how to provide the ‘best education’ to form the next generation of competent leaders from community to the national and global levels, economic planners, scientists, artists, humanists and more generally informed citizens, especially in this fast paced, technology-prone and globalized world” [1]. The global youth wellbeing index includes 35 indicators stretching over 7 domains which include education, gender equality, safety and security, citizen participation, health, economic opportunity and ICT [2]. The Sustainable Development Goal 4 which is the quality education goal aims to “ensure inclusive and equitable **quality education** and promote lifelong **learning** opportunities for all” and this demands all universities to provide a better education in nurturing balanced graduates [3].

The relevance of education cannot be overemphasized as it is an essential human right that every human deserves. Teaching and research in higher education have been typically prioritized as the main agenda and determinant for promotion of faculty members and this is due to the fact that little attention is given to community engagement [4].

According to the 2017 Global Youth Wellbeing Index by International Youth Foundation, the world today has a larger generation of youth than ever before. Half of the global population is now under the age of 30, which is having a dramatic impact on every aspect of the society. When these young people are educated, engaged and empowered, they can become effective agents of change, shaping the world for a better place to live. But when their needs are overlooked, we see alarming trends of a growing number of young people who are unemployed, under-educated, and generally disaffected [5]. The question in this paper is: “are we creating a world in which B40 youth in Nigeria can enhance their wellbeing and become successful working adults, parents and citizens?”

This paper proposes a conceptual Malaysian UoTf business model – in the form of BMC (Business Model Canvas) and VPC (Value Proposition Design Canvas, that will help to highlight key value propositions and benefits of international community engagement, show what universities should pay attention to and transform present day universities into universities of the future by leveraging on digital capabilities and platforms, and are relevant in the digital era through humanizing entrepreneurship education. The BMC is a new business paradigm which consists of nine building blocks [6]. These nine building blocks of the BMC are namely: customer value proposition, customer segment, customer relationships, key activities, key partners, channels, revenue streams, key resources and cost structures.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Nigeria is a country with a current approximate population of 200 million people and it has a total number of 36 states, and consists of six geo political zones namely; south-south, south-east, south-west, north-central, north-east and north-west with 774 local government areas.

The concept of sustainable development in any country is a noteworthy one that will certainly have challenges especially in developing nations such as Nigeria, as the state of the socio-economic, infrastructural and human development is still in a lamentable state with several hindrances opposing its growth [7]. The youths make up the most significant part of the world’s population and are the most vibrant, creative, contributive and diligent people. Even though they can prove to be more productive in any of life’s field, ironically, a large percentage of them still are unemployed. They represent one fifth of the world’s population and half of the total unemployed global workforce. One of the biggest social challenges in Nigeria currently is the large scale of youth’s unemployment due to non-empowerment of youths through entrepreneurship education. Some dangers amongst numerous ones of the non-empowerment of the youth include: low self-esteem and frustration, vulnerability of the youngsters which can make them turn to drugs and commit crimes, exposure to bigger risk of lower wages in the future, cost of putting training programs together will be too much for the government due to a high number of unemployed youths, high dependence on others such as family members, friends etc. due to lack of inadequate income and mental/health issues as a result of isolation that often accompanies unemployment. Given these dangers, the non-empowerment of the youth has led to social, political and economic issues which in turn has skyrocketed negative vices such as hunger, poverty, kidnapping, frustration, terrorism & insurgencies etc. [8]. There are barriers that prevents youth from venturing into business ownership and they include: acquisition of relevant skills, relevant institutional supports, access to credit, access to information and access to market. The level of entrepreneurship awareness is low and there is limited access to mentoring programs which also makes it difficult for youths to be able to identify, begin, nurture and sustain a business as mentoring is generally considered to be useful when starting a new business venture [9].

[4] declared after conducting a research and data analysis in a Nigerian university in Kwara state, that four factors were discovered to be the barriers barricading the professors’ participation in community engagement activities and outreaches and they were: a.) Lack of funds to execute community development projects b.) Resistance to change by community members c.) Educational gap between academics and community members d.) Time constraints due to multiple engagements. Furthermore, the explanation that resistance to community engagement outreach may be partially because it has not been institutionalized in higher education system was given. Despite Nigeria having the largest universities in the Sub-Sahara Africa, the documentary evidence of university and faculty members’ community engagement outreach is still deficient.

3. OBJECTIVE

The main objective of this paper is to devise solutions utilizing a conceptual business model that can enhance the wellbeing of B40 youths in Nigeria through university international community engagement activities and digital platform in order to:

- Provide graduates with the necessary skills that will equip them with the manpower society needs
- Provide purposeful education for the youths that can make them self-reliant and generate income for themselves
- Produce youths who are job creators rather than job seekers
- Stimulate the economic and industrial growth of less developed places
- Provide graduates with adequate trainings that can make them become innovative in recognizing new business windows of opportunity

4. METHODOLOGY

This paper adopted the design and system thinking approach to develop a conceptual business model of a Malaysian-based UotF - focusing on conducting relevant community engagement and humanizing entrepreneurship education activities with products/services/solution and digital platform for enhancing the wellbeing of B40 youth in Nigeria. The conceptual business model is developed through understanding the needs of B40 youth in Nigeria by using business modeling tools i.e. Business Model Canvas (BMC) and Value Proposition Design Canvas (VPC). The approach involves carrying out a literature review and interviews to identify key issues of the Customer Segment, formulating and devising an initial business model – in the form of BMC and VPC, and value proposition that helps to enhance wellbeing of B40 youth in Nigeria. The initial BMC is validated by interviewing academicians and graduates. And the initial VPC is validated by interviewing several students in institutions of higher learning and academicians. Design thinking is a design methodology that provides a solution-based approach to solving problems.

5. LITERATURE REVIEW

People can break the harsh cycle of poverty when they are able to obtain quality education, also inequalities can be reduced and more people can be empowered to live more sustainable and healthy lives. Education promotes tolerance in people and makes the society more peaceful (Nazar et al., 2018). The University of the Future aims to set up institutions of higher learning as a network that renders universities, industry, students and staff social interaction. It builds a partnership relationship between students, universities and the communities [6].

a. Sustainable Development Goals 1, 3, 4 and 8

Via education, other sustainable development goals can be attained. Education is considered to be top priority of the UNESCO as it is included as part of the basic human rights and is helpful in building peace in the society and attaining sustainable development (Nazar et al., 2018). SDG4 (quality education) which has a 2030 target to ensure that all learners acquire the knowledge and skills required to promote sustainable development through education for sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, promotion of a culture of peace and non-violence, global citizenship and appreciation of cultural diversity and of culture's contribution to sustainable development, contributes to SDG1(no poverty) which seeks to end poverty in all its forms everywhere with few of its targets being to ensure the mobilization of resources from a variety of sources in order to provide adequate and predictable means for developing countries to implement programmes and policies that will end poverty in all its proportions; and also to create sound policy frameworks at the national, regional and international levels based on pro-poor and gender-sensitive development strategies that will support an increased investment in poverty eradication actions; SDG3(good health and wellbeing) which seeks to enhance good health and wellness and has targets to strengthen the prevention and treatment of substance abuse, including narcotic drug abuse and harmful use of alcohol, as well as to strengthen the implementation of the World Health Organization Framework Convention on Tobacco Control in all countries, as appropriate; and SDG8 (decent work and economic growth) which seeks to promote inclusive and sustainable economic growth, employment and decent work for all and has a target to promote development oriented policies that support productive activities, job creation, entrepreneurship, creativity and innovation, and also encourage the growth of small scale and medium sized enterprises as well as through access to financial services.

b. Institutes of higher learning and Uotf

According to [10], the higher institutions of learning sought innovative solutions that will provide students with experiences that better equips them for the workforce. The trend goes beyond innovations that are related to institutional operations, generating a chance for institutions of higher learning seeking to establish a culture of innovation for their learners. These entrepreneurial campus partnerships accord students the opportunity to learn skills beyond conventional disciplinary knowledge and focus on workforce preparedness, giving graduates an edge when they enter the labor market. Faculties have the chance to absorb dynamic experiences into their coursework, and students who enter the workforce with the exposure gotten from the entrepreneurial mind-set are more ready for rapidly progressing business sectors.

Various challenges in the period of eight years that obstruct the adoption of technology in higher education were identified in the figure below.

Figure 1.

The technology development picked by the 2019 Horizon Expert Panel have the prospective to expand access and convenience, improve the teaching profession, leverage data, foster authentic learning, spread digital fluency, and stimulate further innovation. Important developments in educational technology for higher education between the years 2012 and 2019 are identified below:

- Analytics Technologies
- Adaptive Learning Technologies
- Games and Gamification
- The Internet of Things
- Mobile Learning
- Natural User Interfaces
- Bring Your Own Device
- Makerspaces
- Flipped Classroom

- Wearable Technology
- 3D Printing
- Tablet Computing
- Artificial Intelligence
- Next-Generation LMS
- Affective Computing
- Mixed Reality
- Robotics
- Quantified Self
- Virtual Assistants
- Massive Open Online Courses
- Blockchain

[11] mentioned and explained that there are five megatrends that will give impacts in the coming decades to the higher education sector and they include:

- Contestability of markets and funding; which entails universities competing for students and funds from the government.
- Integration with the industry; which calls for the building of relevant relationships between the higher education institutions and the industry in the coming decade so as to support the application and funding of research, distinguish the teaching and learning programs, and strengthen the role of HEI as main drivers of innovation and growth. ,
- Digital technologies; that will metamorphose the manner in which education is accessed and passed on, and how value is created by the higher education institutes of learning.
- Democratization of knowledge and access; which involves the immense increase in the availability of knowledge digitally and the extension of access to higher education in developing and developed markets. This will make a pivotal change in the role higher institutions play as inventors and custodians of knowledge.
- Global mobility; which will boost competitiveness, bring opportunities for deeper partnerships globally and a wider access to students and academic talents. This will make headway for students, academics and university brands.

Furthermore, other drivers of change as presented by UTM internationals' senior director in a seminar were mentioned by the authors and they are:

- Research and innovation
- Access and equity
- University funding
- Global reputation
- University funding

c. Balanced entrepreneurship education

Ron Miller defined a balanced education as “a philosophy of education based on the premise that each person finds identity, meaning and purpose in life through connections to the community, to the natural world and to humanitarian values such as compassion and peace. It aims to call forth from people an intrinsic reverence for life and a passionate love of learning” [12]. Entrepreneurship education is the acquiring of practical knowledge and skills that are imparted concurrently for self-reliance and employment. Entrepreneurship education will enhance the sustainability of youth empowerment through: leadership, morale and discipline, self-employment, competence and skill based hard work, time management, increased

productivity and poverty alleviation, utilization of technologies, secret of staying in self-employment, preparation for useful living and utilization of potentials. Furthermore, the authors went on to highlight the constraints to entrepreneurship education in Nigeria and some include: lack of access to information, hostile government policies, poor credit and financial system, inadequate expert, inadequacies between education and training, population growth, technological advances, insecurity, inadequacy of power supply, and the retirement age not being favorable for the youth. [8]. In agreement with [13], the government should have a priority target that by 2030 it is ensured that everyone acquires knowledge and skills that will enhance a sustainable level of economic development and lifestyle, human rights, peace and non-violence, gender equality as well as appreciation of culture diversity and global citizenship.

d. How IR4.0 technology enables the enhancement of societal wellbeing

The utilization of ICT can upgrade the quality of education, expand learning opportunities and make education reachable to everyone. The well-known roles ICT play can be observed in the advancing knowledge and skills necessary for productive functioning in the modern world. ICT has made it possible for instruction to be brought to people's homes via radio and T.V broadcast as well as through the internet. The disabled and students with special learning needs could be provided with varying learning milieu utilizing suitable technological devices that can help them develop their potentials, for example the use of braille by the visually impaired learner is as a result of technological innovation. In Nigeria, it is necessary to employ ICTs to make education more relevant and productive not just for the school setting but also lifelong learning. In order to compete successfully in the global economic sphere, highly skilled and educated workforce with proficiency in the application of ICT is very vital. This makes the utilization of ICT and knowledge central to education in the 21st century. Stakeholders in education sector in Nigeria are encouraged to be concerned about the best ways to leverage the knowledge economy [1].

The 4th industrial revolution governs the metamorphosis of the entire spheres of production, services, management and governance and leads to digital transformation. Experts in education agreed that innovations will shape education 4.0 and students have to be trained to become innovators. In recent times, our mobile and smart devices, social media and sensors have become an extension of humans. The 4th industrial revolution automates complex tasks integrates artificial intelligence, cloud computing, and internet of things (IOT). Graduates need to be entrepreneurial, innovative and have the cognitive flexibility to deal with complexity and must acquire self-learning skills in order to remain relevant in the era where change is rapid. The working-class need to collaborate with machines as much as they do with man. The IR4.0 will accord students and graduates the opportunity to enhance their digital competency- knowledge, skills and culture. The meeting of man-machine in the IR4.0 era demands students and lecturers to have trans-disciplinary knowledge and skill-sets [11]. The fourth industrial revolution refers to the current and future advancements in the use and usability of technologies which are capable of transforming the workplace. With the advent of the latest groundbreaking phase of automation, the employability skills set required from graduates will unavoidably shift from being more technically focused to being softer and social, i.e. development of soft skills. Soft skills are defined as "skills, abilities and traits that pertain to personality, attitude and behavior rather than to formal or technical knowledge" and are connected to interacting with other persons and demonstrating social skills, confidence and self-reflection. However, that is not to say that hard skills have become irrelevant but rather digital interference will call for the need for graduates to be multi skilled, with the social skills needed to be infused with technical expertise [14].

e. International Community Engagement

Community engagement is recognized as a fundamental function of higher education along with teaching and research which helps to promote environmental, economic and socio-cultural development of communities. Higher education perceives teaching, research and community engagement outreach as separate elements of the academic continuum as community engagement is perceived as additional activities undertaken by academics that contribute to the community wellbeing positively [4]. University-community engagement involves a university having a partnership with a community group to build capacity within the community. Both the university and community work towards goals that are mutually beneficial via this partnership. A lot of students participating in international community engagement projects are opportune to build up their professional practice in an environment that challenges their professional capacities. Besides adding to the quality of their professional practice, their learning can as well contribute to their development as engaged citizens and the accomplishment of graduate attributes desirable for universities that are committed to social justice- hence many faculties have opportunities for students to take part in international community engagement [15].

Focus area	1 Before	2 During	3 After
1 Discipline-specific learning (DSL)			
2 Community-engagement learning (CEL)			
3 Student well-being (SWB)			

Figure 2. The conceptual framework for the support of student learning and well-being during international community engagement [15]

A subsidiary of chevron, CNL, that started oil production in Nigeria in 1961 is in a partnership with the federal government of Nigeria which owns a majority stake in CNL's operations. Those operations spans over five states reaching multiple ethnic groups which includes over 420 communities and 850,000 people. CNL's approach to engagement with these local communities included agreements with individual communities impacted by CNL's operations; which provided funding for small scale projects and homage payments to traditional rulers as well as contracts for work sometimes; and large scale infrastructural development projects which were intended to benefit the entire region. However, the individual agreements with the communities was difficult for the following reasons:

1. There was a lack of transparency which further led to inter-community disagreements and rivalry as each community measured itself against imaginary benchmarks of what other communities were rumoured to have been presented with.
2. There was mistrust as a result of so many agreements and promises including real and perceived ones (miscommunication and misperception about whether a promise had been made or not) made by the company to individual communities that went unfulfilled.
3. Even though the individual agreements included funding for local development projects, the development results to show for them were few as community leaders ended up enriching themselves.
4. There were more than 400 separate community agreements which were individually negotiated and whenever operational realities required any change in the existing state of affairs, new negotiations were needed to be made with each community. Hence, agreements were uncontrollable from the perspective of CNL [16].

The federal government of Nigeria introduced a programme called the YouWin programme which was launched in 2011 as an innovative business plan competition, in a renewed effort made by the multilateral agencies to promote small and medium enterprises (SMEs) financing and encourage microeconomic development by generating the private sector employment. The objective of the programme is to create jobs by aiding young and aspiring Nigerian entrepreneurs to start and implement business ideas as well as employ others. Through this, the aspiring youth will be accorded the opportunity to present their business insight and skills to investors, mentors, and business leaders. Three editions of the programme have been implemented and the business plans were assessed by the Pan African University while quality assurance was provided by Plymouth business school in the United Kingdom (UK) and then an award of grants to the selected awardees [17].

f. Information literacy

Women and men, the poor and the vulnerable having equal rights to economic resources, ownership and control over properties, financial services, natural resources and inheritance, etc. would depend on the extent of access to relevant and necessary information. This type of information cannot be retrieved only via traditional literacy, therefore the need for information literacy. Although information literacy would be enhanced by the traditional literacy as it would be tasking for a person who can neither write nor read to be able to access information through the use of ICT tools. Hence traditional literacy should not be underestimated while encouraging information literacy for sustainable development [18].

6. INITIAL BUSINESS MODEL – INITIAL BMC

Table 1. Initial Business Model Canvas

7. VALIDATION OF THE INITIAL BUSINESS MODEL AND KEY FINDINGS

Validation of the initial BMC and VPC: The initial BMC was developed off literature reviews based on research findings from the authors. The BMC was validated by the Director of International Unit of IIUM and VPC validated by the various CS. An interview was conducted with fifteen (15) Nigerian university students and two (2) lecturers from different universities, as well as with three (3) graduates who were all interviewed via online platform. The following findings were unraveled after conducting interviews:

- 57.1% of the interviewees are not familiar with the SDGs hence the need for the international community engagement by the Malaysian UotF.
- 90% agreed that Nigerian universities are not doing enough to achieve any of the SDGs. Only a few higher institutions of learning actually involve students in the active participation in community services. In three of the universities, there have been volunteer services by the medical students where they rendered services such as sensitizing people on public health challenges, help out in local health centers and conducting free eye test for people around the community.
- 69.2% say that their universities have never organized any community engagement services.
- 63.6% agree that international community engagement can help to reduce poverty, create employment and instill the willingness to be entrepreneurial in Nigerian youths
- Just a few universities have held conferences to address the SDGs issues existing in their immediate surroundings.
- Young people need to be well trained and equipped to be able to contribute positively to the wellbeing of their society by their participation in and contribution to community engagement.

8. VALIDATED BUSINESS MODEL (BMC)

Table 2. Validated Business Model Canvas

8.1 Value Proposition (VP):

The VPs are the values and benefits to be offered by the Malaysian UotF that include: Balanced entrepreneurship education, Societal-wellbeing and value creation, Empowered youths, Trainings, Employment, Reduced poverty, Coaching, Mentoring and Access to information. The SDGs 1, 3, 4 and 8 are the major focus for the delivery of these value propositions.

8.2 Customer Segment (CS):

Customer Segment are the recipients of the value propositions & benefits offered by the Malaysian Uotf. The customer segments which include (B40 youth, communities, and poor families) will receive the VP of balanced entrepreneurship education, societal wellbeing, access to information, reduced poverty, and mentoring) and (students, academics, donors, and sponsors) will receive the value propositions of value creation, and access to information). Both groups can work together.

8.3 Customer Relationship (CR):

The customer relationship describes how the Malaysian UotF aims to establish and keep the relationship with the customer segment in order to continuously stay connected with them and deliver the VPs to various CS. The ways through which this relationship can be established and maintained for this project is by: Digital platform (DP), Seminars, coaching and mentoring. The key functionality of the digital platform is to provide a means to effective communication.

8.4 Channels:

Channels indicate the platforms through which the delivery of the value propositions can be achieved. The channels include: Digital platforms (DP) and Face to face, masjid, and partners' outlets. The functionality of the DP is to provide access to the VPs.

8.5 Key Activities (KA):

This involves the necessary activities that must be put in place to ensure that the goals of the value propositions delivery to the customer segment are met. These activities include: International community engagement, Develop & enhance DP, Humanizing digital entrepreneurship education, and Training programs.

8.6 Key Resources (KR):

These are the relevant funds, people and materials that are needed to deliver the value propositions to the customer segments. The key resources required include: ICT platform, Students, Alumni, Funds, research & innovation IPs and outputs, and Skilled workforce.

8.7 Key Partners (KP):

This describes the partnership between people and/or organizations who can function together to carry out the plan of delivering the value propositions to the various customer segments offered by the Malaysian University of the Future. The key partners to be involved in this project include: The Government, Universities, Charities & Community foundations, and financial institutions. Universities can partner with communities to initiate projects for international community engagement as well as provide a balanced entrepreneurship education, while the government can provide economic stability, regulate policies and build initiatives that will support empowerment of the B40 youths thereby reducing poverty, promoting well-being and creating employment. The charities, community foundations and banks can provide and assist with fund raising to sponsor trainings which will in turn create value and provide access to information.

8.8 Revenue Streams:

The revenue streams indicate the ways revenue can be generated to implement and run/sustain the project. These revenues streams are as follow: Grants & scholarships from the Government, CSR grants & scholarships from the private companies, donations from Sponsors & Donors, and Zakaat/Waqaf.

8.9 Cost Structure:

This includes the cost that will be drawn from the execution of key activities and hiring/ acquiring key resources in ensuring the delivery of the offered value propositions to the various customer segments, as well as sustaining the operations that will take place. The cost will cover academics salaries, Research, Trainings, technological development & maintenance and engagement activities.

9. VALIDATED VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS (VPC)**Customer profile****Value map**

Customer segment	Job to do	Pains	Gains	Products and services	Pain Relievers	Gain creators
Students	-Volunteer services to the community -Actual projects -Community sensitization	-Lack of funds -Lack of proper awareness -Lack of adequate ICTs	-New skills acquired by practice -Balanced education	-Community engagement -Free services -Experience	-Enhanced learning environment -New skill acquisition and development	-Trainings & participation -Entrepreneurship education -Proper mentoring programmes
Communities (Rural areas & poor people)	-Collaborate with institutions of higher learning	-Inadequate engagement -Lack of access to well-being facilities	-Experience & knowledge acquisition	-Shared and improved experiences	-Adequate & productive engagement -Appropriate response to change	-Proper sensitization -Free rendered services
Academics	-Collaboration with students -Community empowerment	-Lack of time -Inadequate resources	-Improved community well-being	-Engagement platforms -Balanced graduates	-Grants -Responsive community	-Fund availability -Readiness of community
B40 Youths	-Collaborate with Key partners	-Lack of Entrepreneurial training and skills -Unemployment -Low income	-Skills acquisition -Employment -Wellbeing	-Community engagement -Value creation	-Grants -Initiatives -Access to information	-Balanced entrepreneurship education -Skills

Table 3. Validated Value Proposition Canvas

10. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

A lot still needs to be done concerning community engagement in Nigeria. The relationship between the higher institutions of learning and the communities in Nigeria still needs to be improved on and strengthened. Efforts have to be made to proffer solutions to the problems faced by the society in order to bridge the gap and meet the needs of the customer segment by making quality education, employment, well-being and lifelong learning possible - which this project aims to address. This proposed conceptual business model for Malaysian University-of-the-Future with focus on international community engagement can be benchmarked and adapted by other institution of higher learning.

Future work includes formulating and establishing the Project and Change Management Plan in implementing the conceptual and validated Malaysian UotF business model for enhancing the wellbeing of B40 youth in Nigeria through relevant international community engagement and humanizing entrepreneurship education activities and the development of the digital platform.

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